

Employee Resourcing and Service Delivery in Selected Ministries in Enugu State

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How to cite this paper: Ofodeme, Eugenia Amaka | Agbasi, Obianuju Emmanuela | Ani, Ukamaka Teresa "Employee Resourcing and Service Delivery in Selected Ministries in Enugu State" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-5, August 2019, pp.261-265, <https://doi.org/10.31142/ijtsrd25297>

IJTSRD25297

ABSTRACT

This study investigated employee resourcing and service delivery in selected ministries in Enugu State. The study specifically examined the effect of core activities of employee resourcing (ER) which was decomposed into Human Resource Planning (HRP), Recruitment process, Selection & induction, Performance management, Learning & development and Recognition & reward to ascertain their effect on employees' service delivery in Enugu State using an econometric regression model of the ordinary least square. Findings revealed that Human Resource Planning (HRP), Recruitment process, Selection & induction, Performance management, Learning & development and Recognition & reward significantly influence employees' service delivery in Enugu State. Based on the findings the study recommends that Enugu State Civil Service should adhere strictly to the procedure of personnel recruitment and also vigorously follow the core activities of employee resourcing (ER) in the recruitment and retention process to ensure quality service delivery in the state.

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INTRODUCTION

Employees are very important assets of an organization whose well management together with commitment and employment of other assets of the organization, facilitate to the realization of the organizational objectives. It is through their deliberate efforts other assets like machines can be used to produce the expected products. In other words, no matter how much is invested in technology and other modern assets, the achievement of organizational goals and realization of its objectives, highly depends on the effective utilization of qualified and committed human resource as drivers of other resources.

The focus of this study is employee resourcing and service delivery. Although employee resourcing is defined in various ways and different writers have drawn various boundaries around it, the core areas concerned is getting the right people (with appropriate experience, skills, knowledge and other attributes) in the right place at the right time. Armstrong (2012) opines that the term is used as people resourcing, employee resourcing or simply resourcing. It is used to cover employment activities that focus on an organization having the people it needs, and deals with employee turnover and absenteeism issues. The core activities of employee resourcing (ER) include human resource planning (HRP) and moving towards recruitment, selection and induction, performance management, learning and development, as well as recognition and reward. These activities, whether by micro, small, medium, private, public, manufacturing, service or multinational organizations, are conducted in a rapidly changing context. It is significantly about aligning the employees with the strategic and operational needs of the organization and ensuring full utilization of the resources. Armstrong (2001) notes further that it goes beyond obtaining and keeping the number and quality of the required personnel, but also deals with selecting and

promoting people who 'fit' the culture and the strategic needs of the organization. In this study, the author defines employee resourcing as the systematic process of realizing the need to plan for people (HRP), acquiring them through recruitment and selection (R&S), retaining through membership motivation (M) and putting them to the most effective use through employee motivation to higher productivity in order to help the organization achieve its goals.

Statement of the Problem

This study is was informed by public outcry on the perceived poor service delivery from the employees of the Enugu Civil Service, Enugu State, which also cuts across other states of the federation. Service delivery in the Nigeria public sector has not been a success story. Rather, the Nigeria public sector has repeatedly been on the rating list of the Corruption Perceptions Index of Transparency International as one of the most corrupt public sector of the world (Transparency International, 2017). Arguably, the perceived poor service delivery is not unconnected with employee resourcing. Employees are very important assets of an organization whose well management together with commitment and employment of other assets of the

organization, facilitate to the realization of the organizational objectives. It is through their deliberate efforts other assets like machines can be used to produce the expected products. In other words, no matter how much is invested in technology and other modern assets, the achievement of organizational goals and realization of its objectives, highly depends on the effective utilization of qualified and committed human resource as drivers of other resources. According to Olatunji and Ugoji (2013), there is little or nothing wrong in the normal processes of personnel recruitment but the mode and pattern of following the processes of personnel recruitment is what creates a problem in workplaces. Most organisations refuse to adhere strictly to the procedure of personnel recruitment while some adhere to it but allow a lot of influences to affect their personnel recruitment activities. This tends to affect individual worker performance and the organisational development. Against this backdrop, this study therefore examines employee resourcing and service delivery in selected ministries in Enugu State.

Objectives of the Study

This study examines employee resourcing and service delivery in selected ministries in Enugu State. The study specifically modelled the effect of core activities of employee resourcing (ER) which was decomposed into: - Human Resource Planning (HRP), Recruitment process, Selection & induction, Performance management, Learning & development and Recognition & reward- on employees service delivery in Enugu State.

Employee Resourcing

As cited by Onyeizugbe, Orogbu, and Ike (2016), employee resourcing is part of HRM that focuses on the recruitment and release of individuals from organizations, as well as the management of their performance and potential while employed by the organization (Pilbeam & Corbridge, 2002). Employee resourcing strategies exist to provide the people and skills required to support the business strategy; it is concerned with any means available to meet the needs of the firm for certain skills and behaviour (Armstrong, 2010). Employee resourcing holds the key to success of any organization since it ensures that the right person fit to do the job is acquired in the organization (Kavoo-Linge & Kiruri, 2013). It is concerned with the procedures of obtaining and retaining a workforce with the necessary skills, competences, training, attitudes, knowledge, ethics and values (Karemu, Gikera & Josee, 2014). This is because the organization only hires and retains the right manpower in order to increase its performance (Majumber, 2012; John, 2008). Abomeh (2013) contends that if clear resourcing procedure is followed based on practices then the organization is bound to outperform other businesses in the industry. The core activities of employee resourcing (ER) include human resource planning (HRP) and moving towards recruitment, selection and induction, performance management, learning and development, as well as recognition and reward. It is significantly about aligning the employees with the strategic and operational needs of the organization and ensuring full utilization of the resources. Ogunyomi and Ojikutu (2014) define employee resourcing as the systematic process of realizing the need to plan for people (HRP), acquiring them through recruitment and selection (R&S) retaining through membership motivation (M) and putting them to the most effective use through employee motivation to higher productivity in order to help the organization achieve its goals.

Related Empirical Literature

Anyu, Umoh and Worlu (2017) investigated human resource planning and organizational performance in oil and gas firms in Port Harcourt Using the spearman rank order correlation coefficient, we found out that there is a significant relationship between human resource planning and organizational performance and that the relationship between the variables is moderated by organizational structure. Ezeodili and Nebo (2017) examined the politics of performance appraisal in Enugu State Civil Service Commission and Employee Service Delivery using descriptive statistics and chi square non parametric statistical test. Findings revealed that Enugu State Civil Service Commission has had disagreement in the past with its employees as a result of bias in performance appraisal. It was discovered that the Commission the result of staff appraisal was scarcely used in taking decision of employee promotion. Zirra, Ogbu and Ojo (2017) examined the recruitment and selection strategy on the employee performance in the real sector using descriptive survey research design. The inferential statistics used is the "one sample T-test" to find the level of relationship between recruitment/selection strategy and employee performance. The study revealed that the use of recruitment agency and internal employee recommendation in the recruitment/selection process enables organization to recruit committed and productive employees while the recruitment through the influence of host community leads to organizational inefficiency. Onyeizugbe, Orogbu, and Ike (2016) examined employee resourcing and performance of selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State of Nigeria using descriptive statistics and Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis. Findings of the study revealed that unbiased team deployment strategy can help to sustain service delivery in the oil and gas companies. The study also concludes that an adhoc and largely reactive approach to employee resourcing prevails within the industry in Rivers State. Ohaeri and Chukwu (2016) examined manpower development and employee service delivery: A study of Enugu State Local Government Service Commission using percentages, frequent tables and using Chi square method. It was discovered among other things that, staff training will improve employee's performance in Awka-South Local Government Area. It was observed that management makes effort towards ensuring adequate staff training, and that Staff training will have a significant effect on the output and service delivery of staff of Enugu State Local Government. Kemboi and Onyango (2015) examined the effects of employee resourcing and development practices on organization performance in public secondary schools in Rachuonyo South Sub County using descriptive statistics, correlation statistics and regression analysis. The study found employee resourcing to correlated ($r=0.134$) with organization performance. However the relationship was insignificant ($p=0.163$). The study also found out that employee training and development policies positively and significant affects organizational performance. Using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, ANOVA and regression analysis, Katua, Mukulu and Gachunga (2014) examined the effect of employee resourcing strategies on the performance of commercial banks in Kenya. They found that employee resourcing (recruitment, selection, induction and human resource planning) strategies have a significant positive effect on performance of commercial banks in Kenya. The study established that banks are currently emphasizing on the recruitment of people with high

academic qualifications. Therefore, bank performance is influenced by specific HRM related actions. From this study it is concluded that recruitment, selection, induction and human resource planning strategies can combine to enhance firm performance. Based on the findings, it is also concluded that there is a positive relationship between strategic employee resourcing and employee performance among commercial banks in Kenya. Cania (2014) investigated the impact of strategic human resource management on organizational performance using descriptive statistics. Findings revealed that the organizations had proven that there is significantly change their performance through strategic management of human resources while they also admitted that the organization had been experiencing minor changes in their performance. Ogunyomi and Ojikutu (2014) examined employee resourcing and performance of small and medium enterprises in Lagos State using descriptive statistics and regression analysis. They found that although there is a mild association (0.113) between employee resourcing and performance, it is not strong enough to predict the performance of the sampled SMEs. Most of the owners/managers interviewed opined that retaining employees was one of their greatest challenges but not strong enough to determine the level of their performance as they have always envisaged that some of their staff can leave the organization. Sule and Ugoji (2013) examined the processes through which personnel are recruited into organisation and the impacts of the personnel recruitment on the organisational development using the Spearman Rank correlation Co-efficient, percentage, mean scores and standard deviation. The findings of the study revealed certain recruitment procedures adopted in organisations. It also revealed that the recruitment procedures used in the organisation influence personnel behaviour and performance to a large extent. It further established those factors militating against recruitment processes in organisations as well as its consequences on the personnel and organisational development. Gberevbie (2011) carried out an appraisal of staff recruitment and retention policies of Delta State Civil Service in Nigeria using descriptive statistics. The result shows among others that policies on staff recruitment in the State Civil Service is a mixture of merit, political consideration, element of 'god fatherism' and equal representation of citizens.

From the literature reviewed studies on employees resourcing are rife with researchers investigating the concept/phenomena from various stand points. For example, Anya, Umoh and Worlu (2017) investigated human resource planning and organizational performance in oil and gas firms in Port Harcourt. Onyeizugbe, Orogbu and Ike (2016) examined employee resourcing and performance of selected oil and gas companies in Rivers State of Nigeria. Kemboi and Onyango (2015) examined the effects of employee resourcing and development practices on organization performance in public secondary schools in Rachuonyo South Sub County. Katua, Mukulu and Gachunga (2014) examined the effect of employee resourcing strategies on the performance of commercial banks in Kenya. Cania (2014) investigated the impact of strategic human resource management on organizational performance and Ogunyomi and Ojikutu (2014) examined employee resourcing and performance of small and medium enterprises in Lagos State. However, the need for this study arises from the fact that there is paucity of empirical study on employees resourcing and service delivery in the civil service

particularly in Enugu State civil service. In other words, none of the studies reviewed were carried out in Enugu State. Again, none of the studies measured that effect of employees resourcing on service delivery particularly in the civil service. This study therefore fills the knowledge and literature gap by investigating employee resourcing and service delivery in selected ministries in Enugu State

Methodology

This section on methodology deals with research design, population of the study, sample size and sampling technique, method of data collection, validity of the instrument and method of data analysis.

Research Design

This research work adopts a descriptive survey research design. It is concerned with the collection of data for the purpose of describing and interpreting existing phenomena. It involved sampling by using structured questionnaire to elicit data that were analyzed so as to get an insight into the topic under consideration.

Population of the Study

It is imperative in any study to determine the group or things or persons to be studied. Population of a study has been described in the literature as the "aggregate of individual persons or objects for investigation, or the sum total of the unit of analysis" (Okeke, 2005; Chukwuemeka, 2006). Generally, two main characteristics of the population are that it can be finite or infinite (Chukwuemeka & Oji, 1999; Okeke, 2001, Hair et al, 2005, Agbonifoh and Yomere, 1999). In the present study, the population comprises of employees of five selected ministries in Enugu State Civil Service. The total numbers of workers as the time of this study from the ministries are one thousand two hundred eleven (1211). The ministries that are randomly selected are ministry of agriculture, ministry of education, ministry of finance, ministry of health and ministry of justice.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

To determine the sample size, for the purpose of questionnaire distribution; the Taro Yamani formula was used. The formula is stated thus: $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$

Where:

N	=	sample size
N	=	population
E	=	Margin of error (5% or 0.05)
I	=	Constant

Substituting in the above formula:

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \frac{1211}{1+1211(0.05)^2} \\ &= \frac{1211}{1+1211(0.0025)} \\ &= \frac{1211}{1+1211(0.0025)} \\ &= \frac{1211}{3.0245} \\ n &\approx 400 \end{aligned}$$

Method of Data Collection

The instrument used for the data collection was questionnaire which was designed and administered to the employees of the Enugu State civil service - which serve as the sample size of the study.

Method of data Analysis

The data obtained were analyzed using regression analysis and they were presented in the subsequent section. The analysis of the responses of the staff of the Enugu State Civil Service - which serves as the sample size of the study were analyzed using four point summative scale response categories of SA= Strongly Agreed, A= Agreed, D= Disagreed and SD-strongly Disagree. By so doing the respondents will be able to tick the option of their choice. Any item with mean value of 2.5 and above was regarded as agreed while items which have a mean value below 2.5 was regarded as disagree. Out of the 400 questionnaires that were distributed only 372 were dully completed and returned.

The model for the study is stated as follows:

The model is implicitly specified as follows;

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, X_3 \dots\dots X_n + e_i) \tag{eq(1)}$$

The model is explicitly specified as follows;

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 \dots\dots \beta_k X_k + \epsilon \tag{eq(2)}$$

Where:

α = intercept

Y = Consumers patronage (frequency of patronising the bakery).

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \epsilon \dots \tag{eq(3)}$$

The included variables X_1 - X_6 represent Human Resource Planning (HRP), Recruitment process, Selection & induction, Performance management, Learning & development and Recognition & reward. $\beta_1 - \beta_6$ are the slope coefficients of the regressors, α represents the vertical intercept and ϵ the stochastic residual term designed to capture the effects of unspecified variables in the model, which is normally distributed with a mean value of zero.

Findings

Regression Analysis Result

Table3: Regression Result on Employee Resourcing and Service Delivery in selected Ministries in Enugu State.

Model	B	Std. error	T	Sig.
Constant(C)	5.477	0.891	6.147	0.000
Human Resource Planning (HRP)	0.763	0.064	11.922	0.010
Recruitment process	2.911	0.488	5.965	0.000
Selection and induction	0.976	0.167	5.844	0.000
Performance management	0.877	0.143	6.133	0.001
Learning and development	0.884	0.062	14.258	0.025
Recognition and reward	1.711	0.201	8.512	0.001
R	0.815			
R ²	0.763			
Adj. R ²	0.750			
F-statistic	224.112			0.000

Source: Field Survey 2018

Dependent Variable: Employee Service Delivery

To ascertain the effect of Employee Resourcing on Service Delivery in selected Ministries in Enugu State, the weighted mean of the six independent variables were regressed on the dependent variable to enable us determine the nature of relationship between the dependent and independent variables, effect of the six independent variables on the dependent variable, the overall fitness of the model using the F-statistics and probability value and the level of significance of the independent variables in influencing the dependent variables using the t-test and probability value. The table above shows the regression result. It also shows the precision of the model which was analyzed using economic a priori criteria and statistical criteria.

Recruitment process, Selection & induction, Performance management, Learning & development and Recognition & reward) have positive and significant effect on service delivery.

Discussion based on statistical criteria

In order to evaluate the effect of Employee Resourcing on Service Delivery in selected Ministries in Enugu State, the analysis was also done based on statistical criteria by applying the coefficient of determination (R²) and the F-test. In general, the joint effect of the explanatory variables-independent variables-in the model account for 0.763 or 76.3% of the variations in the employees service delivery. This implies that 76.3% of the variations in the employees service delivery is being accounted for or explained by the variations in Human Resource Planning (HRP), Recruitment process, Selection & induction, Performance management, Learning & development and Recognition & reward, while other independent variables not captured in the model explain just 23.7% of the variations in the employees service delivery.

Discussion of Findings

Discussion based on economic a priori criteria

Discussion using this criterion enables us to determine the nature of relationship between the dependent and independent variables. In this case, the sign and magnitude of each variable coefficient are evaluated against theoretical or economic a priori criteria/expectations. As showed in the table 3, it is observed that the regression line has a positive intercept as presented by the constant (c) = 5.477. This means that if all the variables are held constant or fixed (zero), employee service delivery will increases by 5.4%. The result also conforms to the a priori expectation. This states that the intercept could be positive or negative, so it conforms to the theoretical expectation (Gujarati, 2008). All the coefficients (Human Resource Planning (HRP),

Summary of Findings, Conclusion and recommendations

In the final analysis, this study has investigated employee resourcing and service delivery in selected ministries in Enugu State. The study specifically modelled the effect of core activities of employee resourcing (ER) which was decomposed into: - Human Resource Planning (HRP), Recruitment process, Selection & induction, Performance management, Learning & development and Recognition &

reward- on employees service delivery in Enugu State. Findings revealed that Human Resource Planning (HRP), Recruitment process, Selection & induction, Performance management, Learning & development and Recognition & reward significantly influence employees' service delivery in Enugu State. Based on the findings the study recommends that Enugu State Civil Service should adhere strictly to the procedure of personnel recruitment and also vigorously follow the core activities of employee resourcing (ER) in the recruitment and retention process to ensure quality service deliver in the state.

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